

MODERN PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY INTO THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article defines primary contextual features of phraseological units in general and promotes their classification in English language. Moreover, the article discusses the issues that may be faced in the process of the translation of phraseological constructions from in English and Uzbek languages.

INTRODUCTION

In modern linguistics, the cultural study of the development of phraseological units in the language shows the relationship between language and culture, because fixed phrases are more related to the life of the people than other linguistic units of the language. They were formed on the basis of centuries-old life experiences, traditions and rituals that continue to this day. Thus, mental qualities are clearly felt. This feature becomes more obvious when phraseological units contain onomastic components. The reason is that onomastic units have become a bridge connecting the people's past and present life. Therefore, separate study of phraseological units in different systematic languages, their etymology, structure, semantics.

It is known that a number of studies have been conducted on phraseological units in world linguistics. Consequently, the works of LABulakhovsky, AVKunin, L. Kulieva, K. Musaev, ISStepanova, EFarsenteva, INIsabekov, AVUrazmetova are important in this regard. is important. EFarsenteva made a comparative analysis of phraseological units representing human nature in the system of different languages; I. Stepanova reviewed the Russian and English system of phraseological units related to flower names. I. Isabekov studied the problems of translation of phraseological units in Kyrgyz and Russian languages. One of the important studies in this regard is ZKKorzyukova's dissertation work on the topic "The main aspects of the function of phraseological units with proper names in the English language." In his research, the most important characteristic of phraseological units in English linguistics is shown as incompatible components, analyzed on the basis of Kunin's "English-Russian dictionary. In his research, he studied the etymology of phrases,

B. Reimov conducted research on phraseological units expressing the emotional state of a person, GE Hakimova studied phraseological units with zoological names, M. Vafoeva researched phraseological synonyms in the Uzbek language, U. Rashidova specially studied

somatic expressions of the Uzbek language. However, phraseological units containing place names in different languages have not been fully studied. In this study, we pay special attention to the wide dissemination and classification of the features and structure of phraseological units with an onomastic component, and are studied on the basis of various systematic linguistics materials and monographs and dissertations on English, Russian, and Uzbek linguistics. . Russian linguist LA

1) formed on the basis of proverbs and stories;

There is many a slip twixt the cup and the lip — don't jump and say "okay", don't rush in advance, don't put a stake on the unborn calf.

Cut the Gordian knot or cut the knot - find a solution to a complicated problem; = to find the tip of the rope.

2) formed on the basis of professional vocabulary;

go for a Burton - die, wink, disappear without a trace. Barton is a small brewing town in Staffordshire.

Write in water — (kqi) to work for nothing.

3) based on jokes and anecdotes;

The smell of the lamp — (ss) the smell of the lamp (in the compound when the writer is writing his work

we are talking about the smell of oil in the lamp that emits light); forced, artificial.

apple of Sodom - a beautiful but nauseating wet fruit;

4) derived from biblical images and passages; Adam' apple - apple, throat apple;

A forbidden fruit - a forbidden wet fruit

5) formed under the influence of the countries of the ancient world;

Achilleus heel or the heel of Achilles — Achilles heel; the only weak point is the location. Cassandra warnings — (ku) a warning about an event that is being ignored but is happening at the same time.

6) formed on the basis of translation of foreign expressions;

The golden age The phrase was found for the first time in the poem "Works and Days" by the poet Hesiod. The poem was written in the era of Saturn, when people lived like gods without worries, without quarrels, without wars, without hard forced labor.

The horn of plenty — rained from the sky, very abundant, abundant.

7) formed on the basis of wise words of writers;

Lares and Penates — (ku) your own house — your death bed. Lar and Penat were patrons of hearths in ancient Rome.

Rise like a phoenix from its ashes.

8) formed on the basis of quotes from the life experiences of famous people;

The unwritten law. Phrases from Plato's philosophical works: Hercules' Pillars or the Pillars of Hercules — 1) check, limit, limit. In the eyes of the ancients, the two opposing rocks on the shores of the Straits of Gibraltar, the present-day Rocks of Gibraltar and the Rocks of Ceuta, marked the end of the inhabited lands of the ancient peoples; 2) (km) according to the ancient Greek myth, Hercules walked all over Europe and Africa without stopping, and left the Pillars of Hercules as a reminder of his journey.

Phraseological units play an incomparable role in conveying the uniqueness, lifestyle, material and spiritual values, history, culture, and traditions of the peoples of the world into their language.

Phraseological units are related to how individuals use language units, as well as the basic rules and language norms that regulate their use. The use of phraseological units in speech, their use in terms of national-cultural universality, differential and paradigmatic features, ways of transition from folk art to literary language, semantic features, artistic-stylistic possibilities, translation in terms of form and meaning explanation in terms of problems, the importance of elucidating their place in the national language, the necessity of a dictionary suitable for modern linguistics is presented.

Speaking about the contextual features of phraseological units, it can be said that there is a classification of phraseological structures according to the context, which are designated as phraseomes and idioms. Contextual features reflecting this type of phraseological units were first distinguished by professor AVKunin. Phraseological and phraseological units are distinguished from free phrases and compound words by their phraseological stability. The theory of stability was also developed by Professor AV Kunin. AV Kunin considers sustainability as a multifaceted concept that includes the following elements:

1. Consistency of Use. This shows that phraseological units are not formed in speech, but are repeated ready-made.
2. Lexical stagnation - means that phraseological units are not interchangeable (for example, red ribbon, mare's nest) or partially interchangeable within the framework of phraseological variation: lexical (skeleton in the closet - skeleton in the closet, blind pig - blind or 'lbars), grammatical (stone heart - stone heart), positional and mixed variants.
3. Lexical stability of phraseological units is used to determine semantic stability. The meaning of the phraseological unit is preserved despite minor changes. It can only be identified, clarified, reduced or enhanced.
4. Syntactic consistency.

According to Kunin, any phraseology that does not have one of these stagnation qualities cannot be considered a phraseological unit.

In this regard, there is a question of translating English idioms into another language, which have only idioms as a characteristic feature, which have a unique, unbroken phraseological uniform structure. Preserving the lexical, semantic and linguistic features of idioms is a very difficult task. From the point of view of genetics, it is known that the structure of the English language differs from the structure of the Uzbek language; they belong to separate language families. As a result, the grammatical structures of different languages differ from each other. There are several affixes in the Uzbek language, for example; the phrase begins with a noun and ends with a verb; there are no prepositions, articles, or gender categories. English has articles, prepositions and affixes.

As a result, trying to translate words, phrases, sentences and especially idioms presents some difficulties. Moreover, the differences in form and meaning between English and Uzbek idioms make translation problematic. For example, "hot under the collar" is literally translated as "hot under the collar", while "tepa sochi tikka boldi" is the Uzbek version of this

expression (hair stand on end). As can be seen from the example, the difficulty in acquiring idioms is related to the disparity in terms of form and meaning.

It should be noted that translating idioms from English to another language is very difficult. Because most of them are bright, inventive, laconic and vague, it is so. In translation, it is important not only to express the meaning of the phrase, but also to show its figurativeness, keeping in mind the methodological goal. When translating idioms, the translator must find an equivalent term in the local language and convey their meaning and imagery while preserving the stylistic function of idioms. If there is no equivalent representation in the local language, the translator is forced to settle for an "approximate match". There are examples of phraseological units: At seventh hour - the top is in the minute, the top is in the person.

Beat swords into plow-shares - break swords and make plowshares, go to peaceful work, arrive at peaceful days.

The breath of the nostrils is a vital necessity, as necessary as water and air.

Cast one's bread upon the waters to do something without thinking about its correction. The olive branch - the king of olives; a symbol of peace and tranquility. The root of evil love of wealth.

Heap coals of fire on somebody's head - to embarrass, to return evil with good.

CONCLUSION

Differences in the semantic and stylistic functions performed by words with the same real meaning in different languages, as well as differences in the combinations of such words in different languages, are extremely important for both practice and translation theory. They often cause great practical difficulties and are of great theoretical interest, because they differ in the semantic and stylistic functions of words with the same real meaning in different languages, and the way such words enter different languages. due to compound differences.

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